

CEFR-based Evaluation of English Language Tests Targeting B1 and B2 Levels in a Preparatory Program: A Case Study

Nurgül BEKDEMİR¹ & İsmail Fırat ALTAY²

¹ Ordu University, Ordu, TÜRKİYE
nurgulbekdemir@odu.edu.tr

ORCID: 0000-0002-9107-2653

² Hacettepe University, Ankara, TÜRKİYE
ifaltay@hacettepe.edu.tr

ORCID: 0000-0003-0567-1818

Article Information

Submission	12/01/2025	Revision received	17/06/2025
Acceptance	28/08/2025	Publication date	01/10/2025

Keywords:

CEFR alignment

Language assessment

Intermediate-level language tests

Case study

Abstract: This study aims to investigate the alignment of the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR) with B1 and B2 level language tests conducted at a preparatory school of a state university in Turkey. Based on the qualitative data collected from comparisons of CEFR-based tests and CEFR illustrative scales, this study employed a qualitative case study design to explore whether the applied tests align with the target levels regarding the CEFR. The sample included 4 B1-level tests and 5 B2-level tests assessing four main skills and two language components. The purposive sampling method was used in the study. Document analysis, a qualitative research approach, was used to analyze data. Findings indicated that the exams showed more substantial alignment with CEFR descriptors in specific productive skills, whereas receptive and mediation skills demonstrated weaker alignment. This study contributes to the expanding literature of language assessment based on the CEFR through an in-depth case study approach, with practical implications for EFL lecturers in the testing offices and directors of the preparatory school at universities, ELT departments at universities, policymakers in language testing, and CoHE in Turkey.

Anahtar Sözcükler:

AODÇ ile uyum

Dil ölçme değerlendirme

Orta düzey dil testleri

Durum çalışması

Bir Hazırlık Programında B1 ve B2 Seviyelerini Hedefleyen İngilizce Dil Testlerinin AODÇ Temelli Değerlendirilmesi: Bir Durum Çalışması

Özet: Bu çalışma, Türkiye’de bir devlet üniversitesindeki hazırlık okulunda uygulanmış B1 ve B2 seviyelerindeki dil testlerinin Avrupa Ortak Dil Çerçevesi (AODÇ) ile uyumunu araştırmaktadır. AODÇ temelli testler ile AODÇ betimleyici ölçekleri arasındaki karşılaştırmalardan elde edilen nitel verilere dayanarak, bu çalışma, uygulanan testlerin AODÇ kapsamındaki hedef düzeylerle uyumlu olup olmadığını incelemek amacıyla nitel bir durum çalışması deseni kullanmıştır. Örneklem, dört temel dil becerisini ve iki dil bileşeninden oluşan 4 adet B1 seviyesinde ve 5 adet B2 seviyesinde uygulanmış dil testlerinden oluşmaktadır. Amaçlı örneklem yöntemi kullanılmıştır. Nitel araştırma yaklaşımlarından olan doküman analizine başvurulmuştur. Bulgular, sınavların bazı üretimsel becerilerde CEFR tanımlayıcılarıyla daha güçlü bir uyum gösterdiğini, buna karşılık alıcı beceriler ve aracılık becerilerinde daha zayıf bir uyum sergilediğini ortaya koymuştur. Bu çalışma, AODÇ’ye dayalı dil ölçme ve değerlendirme alanında gelişen literatüre detaylı bir durum çalışması yaklaşımıyla, üniversitelerin hazırlık okullarının ölçme değerlendirme birimlerinde görevli olan yabancı dil olarak İngilizce öğreten öğretim elemanları ve yöneticilerine, üniversitelerdeki İngiliz Dili Eğitimi bölümlerine, dil ölçme ve değerlendirme alanındaki paydaşlara ve Türkiye’deki Yükseköğretim Kurulu’na (YÖK) yönelik pratik çıkarımlar sunmaktadır.

To Cite This Article: Bekdemir, N., & Altay, İ. F. (2025). CEFR-based evaluation of English language tests targeting B1 and B2 levels in a preparatory program: A case study. *Novitas-ROYAL (Research on Youth and Language)*, 19(2), 132–148. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17075902>

1. Introduction

In today's globalized academic environment, English proficiency has become a fundamental prerequisite for university students, especially in English as a foreign language (EFL) contexts. English preparatory programs at universities serve a significant function of preparing students with the language skills required to survive in academic settings, as language proficiency in English Medium Instruction (EMI) programs is the strongest predictor of academic achievement (Curle et al., 2024). In the Turkish higher education context, the Council of Higher Education (CoHE) is responsible for establishing quality assurance mechanisms for all higher education institutions (Council of Higher Education, n.d.). However, preparatory schools are autonomous in setting standards for their language programs, including curriculum, materials, and assessments. Although centralized management of language programs across universities is neither defined by the CoHE nor empirically grounded, some universities adopt the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR) for their programs (Özdemir-Yilmazer, 2022).

Language assessment is designed and applied through internal tests at preparatory schools in Turkey. However, assessment based on the CEFR plays a critical role in ensuring that students are adequately equipped with the necessary skills, as the B1 level is generally considered a threshold for academic readiness in EMI programs at universities (CoE, 2020). Moreover, the B2 level is perceived as the target level for universities to aim for in academic studies (British Council, 2015). Concerns have emerged regarding how effectively the internal tests designed for both B1-level and B2-level proficiency align with the CEFR descriptors (Alderson et al., 2006; Davidson & Fulcher, 2007; Green, 2017; Sridhanyarat et al., 2021; Zheng et al., 2016). It could be observed that there are inconsistencies in the application of the CEFR (Arikan, 2016; British Council, 2015; Mirici & Şengül, 2020). Accurate interpretation of the CEFR scales and their alignment with the language tests is of importance, especially in test design and assessment practices (Alderson, 2007; Davidson & Fulcher, 2007; Demirel, 2020). In addition, the perception of teachers and learners on CEFR-based practices has a crucial effect on the consistency of its application and standardization (Staub & Kirkgöz, 2019; Yüce & Mirici, 2022; Zorba & Arikan, 2016). Thus, it highlights the need for a systematic evaluation of B1 and B2 level language tests based on CEFR. Despite research on CEFR-based language assessment, a gap remains in the literature regarding its effectiveness from the CEFR perspective, particularly through in-depth case studies in the Turkish EFL context. Therefore, the purpose of the current study is to evaluate B1- and B2-level English language tests applied at a Turkish university preparatory program regarding the alignment with the CEFR.

2. Literature Review

2.1. The CEFR

The Council of Europe (CoE) published the CEFR guiding language education in 2001 (CoE, 2001). Since then, it has had an effect not only on European countries but also on nations worldwide (Argentina, Colombia, USA, China, Japan, Taiwan, New Zealand, etc.), representing a global influence (Alderson, 2007; Byram & Parmenter, 2012; Hulstijn, 2007; Khalifa & French, 2009; North, 2014). It presents descriptors in three basic levels to be used in language teaching, learning, and assessment (CoE, 2001). However, instead of using the horizontal axis, which remains valid, the CEFR illustrates the development of language proficiency on the vertical axis (CoE, 2020).

The CEFR adopts a descriptive approach, which is evident in the standardized description of proficiency levels. It also provides users with illustrative descriptors for four main skills

(CoE, 2001). In contrast, an amendment with the new modes—reception, production, interaction, and mediation—has been introduced in the recent publication (CoE, 2020). Reception tasks are based on oral comprehension, audio-visual comprehension, and reading comprehension. In contrast, production tasks include spoken and written production activities. Additionally, interaction tasks are categorized into three types: spoken interaction, written interaction, and online interaction. Mediation tasks also consisted of mediating a text, concepts, and communication. In addition to the communicative language activities in the CEFR, communicative language competences are provided with three dimensions: linguistic competence, sociolinguistic competence, and pragmatic competence (CoE, 2020). Being comprehensive, transparent, and coherent (CoE, 2001), the CEFR provides “a metalanguage for discussing the complexity of language proficiency and for reflecting on and communicating decisions on learning objectives and outcomes” (CoE, 2018, p. 22).

2.2. Language Assessment and Testing

Language education comprises three interconnected terms: assessment, evaluation, and language tests. First, assessment refers to the systematic measurement of language proficiency through performance tasks, standardized tests, and formative evaluations, which provide ongoing information about learners’ progress (Brown & Abeywickrama, 2019; Demirel, 2020; Yüce & Mirici, 2022). However, evaluation emphasizes making informed judgments and interpretations based on assessment results, considering educational goals, learner needs, and teaching context (Alderson, 2007; Byram & Parmenter, 2012). Language tests form the foundation of both assessment and evaluation through the concrete data on competences of language learners (Demirel, 2020; Green, 2017). These tests can be classroom-based or institutionally developed internal tests, or standardized, and they are aligned with frameworks such as the CEFR to enhance validity and transparency (CoE, 2001, 2018; Davidson & Fulcher, 2007; Sridhanyarat et al., 2021).

2.3. Language Assessment Policy in Europe

The European Union and the Council of Europe are institutions that form the language policy in Europe (Jones & Saville, 2009). Its evolution lasted over thirty years, which could be divided into three crucial periods. The first period, spanning the late 1980s and 2002, focused on improving language competence, as language was considered the most significant aspect in addressing challenges regarding employment, mobility, economic growth, and globalization. Thus, the EU provided financial support for language education and multilingualism. The second period, spanning 2002 and 2015, saw the CoE release the CEFR, which facilitates a framework for the syllabi, curriculum, materials, and assessment in language education (CoE, 2001). Beginning in 2015, integrated approaches to learning, teaching, and assessment have emerged to enhance social integration through education. Thus, the effect of the CEFR on European language policy has been considerable due to its descriptive nature in teaching, learning, and assessment (Jones & Saville, 2009).

2.4. Language Assessment Policy in Turkey

Turkey is not currently a member of the European Union; however, the aim of being a member of the EU has improved the language policy in Turkey with the help of necessary education policies, transformation in the education system, and harmonization with the EU standards (Arikan, 2016; Pekdoğan et al., 2023). The CEFR plays a significant role in standardizing language teaching and learning practices, including curriculum design, instructional materials, and assessment procedures (CoE, 2001, 2018).

In Turkey, CoHE supports universities' autonomy in developing their language teaching system, provided they adhere to the basics outlined in the Regulation on the Principles to be Observed in Foreign Language Teaching (Presidency of the Republic of Turkey, 2016). According to Article 49 of the Higher Education Law No. 2547, the Schools of Foreign Languages (SFLs) are responsible for preparing university students to be proficient at the target level of the required language (Presidency of the Republic of Turkey, 2016). Even if many Turkish universities aim to achieve a B2 level proficiency, assessments indicate that the actual proficiency level often remains around B1+ (British Council, 2015). In this context, CEFR-aligned language assessment is crucial for measuring and promoting academic achievement, providing both formative and summative feedback to learners and institutions (Green, 2017; Mirici & Şengül, 2020).

Language assessment practices in Turkey, guided by the CEFR, yielded important advantages and crucial challenges in the higher education context. These practices enhance curriculum standardization, improve learner autonomy through self-assessment opportunities, and provide the use of task-based and blended learning methodologies, enabling authentic language use and student engagement (Demirdöven, 2025; Dunifa, 2023; Sakarya-Akbulut & Mirici, 2024; Zorba & Arıkan, 2016). Also, these contributions enhance the quality assurance, transparency, and comparability across higher education institutions. However, challenges still remain, such as inconsistent teacher readiness in the interpretation of CEFR descriptors, diversity in internal test designs, and the discrepancy between the target proficiency levels (B2) and the actual student outcomes (often B1+) (British Council, 2015; Saral & Balçıkınlı, 2025; Sridhanyarat et al., 2021; Zorba, 2025). To enhance language assessment practices in Turkish higher education, improvements are needed in ongoing professional development, policy changes, and evidence-based evaluation.

2.5. CEFR-related Language Assessment Studies

The CEFR has been investigated concerning different perspectives of language teaching and learning in recent years. It was utilized in order to develop an instrument based on the CEFR level (Alderson et al., 2006). Named “the Dutch CEFR Construct Project,” it investigated whether the CEFR might be the guidance for the test construction in reading and listening skills. The Grid was developed in order to align test items, texts, and tasks with the target levels of the CEFR. Besides developing instruments, arguing that the CEFR could be a practical foundation for constructing language tests, Davidson and Fulcher (2007) emphasized the requirement of effect-driven language test development based on the CEFR, with the priority of taking the effects of tests on learners, curriculum, and teaching methods into account. Also, a proficiency test based on the CEFR was developed by Sridhanyarat et al. (2021), who created a valid and reliable test including four main skills. Moreover, Yüce and Mirici (2022) investigated the implementation of self-assessment practices based on the CEFR, which focused on a different type of assessment. It was revealed as a main result that the ‘can-do’ statements presented as a self-assessment tool in the course materials did not correspond to the CEFR descriptors. A different perspective emerged from the alignment of different frameworks based on writing and speaking skills (North & Piccardo, 2023). It focused on aligning the Canadian Language Benchmarks (CLB) with the CEFR, resulting in high similarity between these frameworks, with only minor nuances in the aforementioned skills. In recent years, the connection between language tests and the CEFR has become a growing focus of the literature. The manual for relating examinations to the CEFR (CoE, 2009) was utilized through its steps in the linking procedure (Green, 2017), indicating the challenges in the alignment process. However, limited attention has been paid to evaluating

language tests based on the CEFR, especially in terms of how accurately intermediate English tests reflect the CEFR descriptors and align with the target levels. Regarding the research gap in the evaluation of language tests about the CEFR in Turkey, this research addresses the following research question:

1. Do the applied tests match the learning outcomes of the target level according to the CEFR criteria?

3. Method

3.1. Research Design

This research employs a case study design to evaluate the language tests designed at the B1 and B2 levels of the CEFR. In this study, each proficiency level was treated as a separate case (i.e., the B1-level tests form one case and the B2-level tests form another). This approach enables a more reliable and comprehensive understanding of the alignment between the applied tests and the CEFR descriptors. The research design provides an in-depth understanding of the context under investigation, namely, the assessment of language proficiency at the B1 and B2 levels at the preparatory school of a state university (Baxter & Jack, 2008). A case in this study refers specifically to the set of tests at each CEFR level. In addition, the collective case study method is adopted, as multiple tests at each level are analyzed to investigate general patterns and phenomena, thereby enhancing understanding and contributing to theoretical development (Creswell & Creswell, 2018).

3.2. Data Collection Instruments

Qualitative data were collected through two instruments. The first instrument consisted of the language tests designed for B1 and B2 levels, encompassing four main skills (listening, reading, writing, and speaking) and two sub-skills (grammar and vocabulary), along with their respective objectives. A total of four B1-level tests and five B2-level tests were included. These tests were developed by the lecturers in the Testing Office of the preparatory school. Test items were selected from the assessment packs provided by Oxford and Express Publishing coursebooks, which are designed based on the CEFR levels. This approach ensured content validity by aligning test items with the CEFR descriptors.

The second instrument included the B1-level and B2-level illustrative scales of the CEFR that comprise reception, production, interaction, mediation, and linguistic competence (CoE, 2020). First, reception, including listening and reading skills, is the ability to understand the language input. Second, production, applied to speaking and writing skills, refers to the ability to produce language output independently, e.g., delivering a monologue or writing a report or essay. Third, interaction involves using language in communication, both in spoken and written forms; for instance, informal discussion with friends and writing notes, messages, and forms. Next, mediation means the ability to convey or transform meaning among participants or sources, such as translating, summarizing, or paraphrasing information for others. Lastly, linguistic competence scales, such as vocabulary range and grammatical accuracy, were used to evaluate the objectives for the grammar and vocabulary parts of the tests. All the descriptors included in these CEFR scales were used to map the test objectives, revealing the alignment rate of each skill and sub-skill with the target levels. The mapping process provided that reception, production, interaction, mediation, and underlying linguistic competence at target levels were explicitly evaluated in the alignment analysis.

Both instruments were utilized to make comparisons and reveal the alignment rate of language tests with the target levels regarding the CEFR. The purposive sampling method

was adopted in order to achieve a rigorous focus on the phenomenon (Creswell & Creswell, 2018; Schoch, 2020). For this research, all the tests applied in the 2023-2024 academic year in the compulsory preparatory program were utilized, as an intermediate level of proficiency was the required level for academic purposes, and a collection of the tests at both the B1 level and the B2 level could give an in-depth understanding of the case.

3.3. Data Collection Procedure

Data were collected during the 2023-2024 academic year over a period of nine months, during which the language tests were continuously administered. The B1-level tests were applied during the first semester, whereas the B2-level tests were administered in the second semester. After each test was administered, mapping objectives to the CEFR descriptors was conducted. This procedure was repeated for each test during the academic year.

First, the language tests for the target levels were prepared based on the assessment materials provided by CEFR-aligned coursebooks (Oxford and Express Publishing), without pre-determined objectives assigned to each test item. Second, after each test was conducted, the objective of each test item was identified and mapped to the relevant CEFR descriptors of the illustrative scales (CoE, 2020). To explain the mapping procedure in detail, the objectives of listening skills in the tests were matched with the oral and audio-visual comprehension scales in the reception mode of the CEFR. In contrast, those of reading skills in the tests were mapped onto the reading comprehension scales. Moreover, the objectives in speaking tests were aligned with the descriptors in both oral production and oral interaction scales, as well as those in writing tests, i.e., written production and written interaction scales. For the mediation, all the objectives of the tests were used to reveal the correspondences to the descriptors in the mediation scales. The language use sections in the test, encompassing grammar and vocabulary, were evaluated through the descriptors in linguistic competence scales. Third, after mapping the objectives onto the descriptors, the alignment rate of each skill in each test was calculated, providing an empirical evaluation of the extent to which the tests measured the targeted proficiency level. Lastly, the results for each set of tests were compared to identify a general trend and enable a comprehensive understanding of the alignment of internal tests applied by preparatory schools at state universities.

3.4. Data Analysis

The data were analyzed using a qualitative approach to address the research question. Document analysis was adopted to examine the relationship between the objectives of B1-level and B2-level tests in terms of skills and the CEFR descriptors at the target levels. The alignment process comprised four stages: (1) identification, (2) matching, (3) coding, and (4) interpretation. First, the skill focus and task type of each test item were determined. For instance, if the speaking test requires test-takers to communicate with each other, it is considered an interaction-based speaking test. Second, both objectives of the applied tests and the CEFR illustrative scales were systematically compared and analyzed through comparative analysis. To illustrate the mapping procedure, one of the test objectives in writing skill in Midterm 2, whose target level is B2, was “to write a well-structured essay with five paragraphs,” which corresponds to the descriptor “can produce an essay or report which develops an argument systematically with appropriate highlighting of significant points and relevant supporting detail.” This correspondence demonstrates that the test clearly requires test-takers to demonstrate the systematic development of ideas with an organized structure. Third, test objective-CEFR descriptor correspondences were demonstrated in a comparative table to make the analysis more solid. Lastly, calculations for each skill and sub-skill were conducted,

which provides a comprehensive and solid perspective to ascertain the rate of alignment with the CEFR. In this way, data analysis was supported by concrete evidence from the test objectives. This mapping procedure was repeated for all the skills in each test. Moreover, the reliability of the qualitative analysis was assured in two ways: (1) the same analysis procedure was consistently applied to all exams during the academic year, and (2) the coding and interpretations were cross-checked with two members of the testing office, which enhanced the consistency and objectivity.

4. Findings

The language tests designed for the assessment of B1 and B2 levels were analyzed through CEFR CV illustrative scales (CoE, 2020). Table 1 shows the alignment rates of the skills in Quiz 1, including Listening, Reading, and Language Use skills. The Listening Section of Quiz 1 was aligned with the B1 level at a rate of 61%, with 18 descriptors and 11 objectives. In contrast, the Reading Section of Quiz 1 had an alignment rate of 48%, with 27 descriptors in the CEFR and 13 objectives in the quiz. Next, the Language Use Section was completely aligned with the B1 level (100%), as 13 descriptors and 36 objectives were matched. Lastly, Quiz 1 was aligned with B1 level mediation at a rate of 25.9%, with 15 objectives corresponding to the descriptors (n = 58).

Table 1.

Correspondence Ratio between Quiz 1 and CEFR Skills

	# of Descriptors in CEFR	# of Matching Objectives in Quiz 1	Correspondence with CEFR (%)
Listening	18	11	61
Reading	27	13	48
Language Use	13	36	100
Mediation	58	15	25.9

Table 2 presents the alignment rates of the skills in Quiz 2, encompassing listening, reading, language use, and writing skills. The Listening Section of Quiz 2 was aligned with the B1 level at a rate of 44.4%, with 18 descriptors and eight objectives. In contrast, the Reading Section of Quiz 2 achieved an alignment rate of 51.9%, utilizing 27 descriptors from the CEFR and 14 quiz objectives. Next, the Language Use Section was completely aligned with the B1 level (100%) as there were 13 descriptors and 33 objectives. Then, the Writing Section was aligned with the B1 level at a rate of 28%. However, it was observed that written production skills were found to be aligned with the target level at a rate of 33.3% (n=4) while the alignment rate of written interaction skills was 23% (n=3). Lastly, Quiz 2 was aligned with B1 level mediation at a rate of 23.9%, with 17 objectives corresponding to the descriptors (n = 58).

Table 2.

Correspondence Ratio between Quiz 2 and CEFR Skills

	# of Descriptors in CEFR	# of Matching Objectives in Quiz 2	Correspondence with CEFR (%)
Listening	18	8	44.4
Reading	27	14	51.9
Language Use	13	33	100
Written Production	12	4	33.3
Written Interaction	13	3	23
Writing Total	25	7	28
Mediation	58	17	29.3

Table 3 shows the alignment rates of the skills in Quiz 3, including listening, reading, language use, and speaking skills. In detail, the Listening Section of Quiz 3 aligned with the B1 level at a rate of 55.5%, as it consisted of 18 descriptors and 10 objectives. In contrast, the Reading Section of Quiz 3 had an alignment rate of 37%, with 27 descriptors in the CEFR and 10 objectives in the quiz. Next, the Language Use Section was completely aligned with the B1 level (100%), as there were 13 descriptors and 27 objectives. Then, the Speaking Section aligned with the B1 level at a rate of 23.9%. However, it was observed that spoken production was found to be aligned with the target level at a rate of 77.3%, whereas there was no correspondence to the CEFR descriptors in spoken interaction scales. Lastly, Quiz 3 was aligned with B1-level mediation at a rate of 22.4% with 13 objectives corresponding to the descriptors (n=58).

Table 3.
Correspondence Ratio between Quiz 3 and CEFR Skills

	# of Descriptors in CEFR	# of Matching Objectives in Quiz 3	Correspondence with CEFR (%)
Listening	18	10	55.5
Reading	27	10	37
Language use	13	27	100
Speaking total	71	17	23.9
Spoken production	22	17	77.3
Mediation	58	13	22.4

Table 4 shows the alignment rates of the skills in Midterm 1, including four main skills and language use. First, the Listening Section of Midterm 1 aligned with the B1 level at a rate of 50%, with 18 descriptors and 9 objectives. In contrast, the Reading Section of Midterm 1 had an alignment rate of 29.6%, with 27 descriptors in the CEFR and 8 matching objectives in the exam. Next, the Language Use Section was completely aligned with the B1 level (100%), comprising 13 descriptors and 33 objectives. The Writing Section was aligned with the B1 level at a rate of 32% when both production and interaction scales were taken into consideration. However, it could be seen that written production was found to be aligned with the target level at a higher rate (66.7%). Also, the alignment rate of the Speaking Section with the B1 level was 31% when both production and interaction scales were taken into consideration. However, in terms of Spoken Interaction, the alignment rate with the B1 level was higher (44.9%) as there were 49 descriptors and 22 matching objectives. Lastly, Midterm 1 was aligned with B1 level mediation at a rate of 19%, with 11 objectives corresponding to the descriptors (n = 58).

Table 4.
Correspondence Ratio between Midterm 1 and CEFR Skills

	# of Descriptors in CEFR	# of Matching Objectives in Midterm 1	Correspondence with CEFR (%)
Listening	18	9	50
Reading	27	8	29.6
Language use	13	33	100
Written production	12	8	66.7
Writing total	25	8	32
Spoken interaction	49	22	44.9
Speaking total	71	22	31
Mediation	58	11	19

Table 5 shows the alignment rates of the skills in Quiz 4, including the listening skill and integrated listening and writing (ILW). Consequently, the Listening Section of Quiz 4 aligned with the B2 level at a rate of 57.9%, as there were 19 descriptors and 11 objectives. In contrast, the alignment rate of the ILW Section of Quiz 4 was 6.7%, as there were 16 descriptors in the CEFR and one matching objective in the exam. However, from the written interaction perspective, the alignment rate of ILW Section increased to 14.3%, as there was 1 objective corresponding to 7 descriptors. Lastly, Quiz 4 aligned with B2 level mediation at a rate of 13.6% with 9 objectives corresponding to the descriptors (n=66).

Table 5.

Correspondence Ratio between Quiz 4 and CEFR Skills

	# of Descriptors in CEFR	# of Matching Objectives in Quiz 4	Correspondence with CEFR (%)
Listening	19	11	57.9
ILW Total	16	1	6.7
Written interaction	7	1	14.3
Mediation	66	9	13.6

The table below summarizes the alignment rate of each section of Quiz 5, which comprises reading and writing skills (Table 6). The Reading Section of Quiz 5 was aligned with the B2 level at a rate of 57.1%. Eight descriptors were matched with 14 descriptors. Moreover, the Writing Section aligned with the B2 level at a rate of 43.75%. However, it is notable that the alignment rate dramatically increased to 77.8% in terms of written production, indicating a significant discrepancy between written interaction and written production. Lastly, Quiz 5 was aligned with B2 level mediation at a rate of 15.2% with 10 objectives corresponding to the descriptors (n=66).

Table 6.

Correspondence Ratio between Quiz 5 and CEFR Skills

	# of Descriptors in CEFR	# of Matching Objectives in Quiz 5	Correspondence with CEFR (%)
Reading	14	8	57.1
Written production	9	7	77.8
Writing total	16	7	43.8
Mediation	66	10	15.2

Table 7 demonstrates the alignment rate of language use in Quiz 6. As shown in the table below, Quiz 6 was entirely aligned with the B2 level. Forty-one objectives of language use corresponded to 17 descriptors of linguistic competence at the B2 level. Also, there was no correspondence to the mediation scales of the B2 level.

Table 7.

Correspondence Ratio between Quiz 6 and CEFR Skills

	# of Descriptors in CEFR	# of Matching Objectives in Quiz 6	Correspondence with CEFR (%)
Language use	17	41	100

Table 8 presents the alignment rates of the skills in Midterm 2, including four main skills and language use. The Listening Section of Midterm 2 was aligned with the B2 level at a rate of 63.15 %, with 19 descriptors and 12 objectives. In contrast, the Reading Section of Midterm 2 had an alignment rate of 57.1%, with 14 descriptors in the CEFR and 8 matching objectives in the exam. Next, the Language Use Section was completely aligned with the B2 level (100%) as

there were 17 descriptors and 18 objectives. The Writing Section was aligned with the B2 level at a rate of 43.75% when both production and interaction scales were considered. However, it could be seen that written production was found to be aligned with the target level at a higher rate (77.8%). Then, the alignment rate of the Speaking Section with the B2 level was 36.7% when both production and interaction scales were considered, but in terms of Spoken Production, the alignment rate with the B2 level was higher (100%), as there were 16 descriptors and 18 matching objectives. Lastly, Midterm 2 was aligned with B2 level mediation at a rate of 31.8%, with 21 objectives corresponding to the descriptors (n = 66).

Table 8.

Correspondence Ratio between Midterm 2 and CEFR Skills

	# of Descriptors in CEFR	# of Matching Objectives in Midterm 2	Correspondence with CEFR (%)
Listening	19	12	63.2
Reading	14	8	57.1
Language use	17	18	100
Written production	9	7	77.8
Written total	16	7	43.8
Spoken production	16	18	100
Speaking total	49	18	36.7
Mediation	66	21	31.8

The alignment rate of the Final Exam with the B2 level is clearly evident in Table 9 below. The Listening Section of the Final Exam was aligned with the B2 level at a rate of 36.8%, with 19 descriptors and 7 objectives. In contrast, the Reading Section of Midterm 2 achieved an alignment rate of 50%, matching 14 descriptors in the CEFR with 7 corresponding objectives in the exam. Next, the Language Use Section was completely aligned with the B2 level (100%), as it consisted of 17 descriptors and 24 objectives. The Writing Section was aligned with the B2 level at a rate of 37.5% when both production and interaction scales were taken into consideration. However, it could be seen that written production was found to be aligned with the target level at a higher rate (66.7%). Then, the alignment rate of the Speaking Section with the B2 level was 26.5% when both production and interaction scales were considered, but in terms of Spoken Production, the alignment rate with the B2 level was higher (81.3%), as there were 16 descriptors and 18 matching objectives. Lastly, the Final Exam was aligned with B2 level mediation at a rate of 22.7% with 15 objectives corresponding to the descriptors (n=66).

Table 9.

Correspondence Ratio between Final Exam and CEFR Skills

	# of Descriptors in CEFR	# of Matching Objectives in Final Exam	Correspondence with CEFR (%)
Listening	19	7	36.8
Reading	14	7	50
Language use	17	24	100
Written production	9	6	66.7
Written total	16	6	37.5
Spoken production	16	13	81.3
Speaking total	49	13	26.5
Mediation	66	15	22.7

5. Discussion and Conclusion

The current research investigated which language tests designed for B1 and B2 levels align with the target level of the CEFR. The results revealed a variety in the alignment rates of the

skills at the B1 and B2 levels. The alignment rate of tests targeted at the B1 and B2 levels at CEFR standards would be stated in three categories: high, moderate, and low. The alignment rates were scrutinized skill-based, besides mediation. To start with, the B1 level examinations, particularly the language use sections and production-based speaking skills, demonstrated a high level of alignment with the B1 level. However, there was still room for enhancement to meet CEFR standards. Following them, listening, production-based writing, and interaction-based speaking were moderately aligned with the B1 level of proficiency. However, reading, mediation, writing, and speaking skills in total demonstrated a low level of alignment, which requires a great deal of improvement to be at the B1 level. It was not an expected result for the mediation to have a low level of alignment with the B1 level, as the B1-level tests included the integration of receptive and productive skills, which could be interpreted as mediation according to the CEFR-CV (CoE, 2020). Both the aspects that led to the alignment with B1 level and the ones required for a higher level of alignment would be discussed, as well as the alignment rates from the highest to the lowest. The high alignment rate of the language use at the B1 level was established through the correspondences to general linguistic range, vocabulary range, grammatical accuracy, vocabulary control, and orthographic control, even though phonological control was not tested in any of the exams (CoE, 2020). The results aligned with the idea of having a long-lasting emphasis on written over spoken proficiency in practice (Baldwin & Apelgren, 2018). However, its integration into the tests would help B1-level language tests to assess every aspect of linguistic competence at CEFR standards.

Speaking skills at the B1 level tests revealed various results based on the mode of assessment. Production-based speaking skills demonstrated a high alignment rate, as most objectives in the production-focused tasks corresponded to the CEFR B1 descriptors for oral production. Conversely, interaction-based speaking skills demonstrated a moderate level of alignment, as fewer objectives in the interaction-focused tasks aligned with the CEFR B1 descriptors for interaction. This distinction shows the specific focus of the speaking tests and explains the basis for the reported alignment rates. Overall, speaking skills, which included both production and interaction, showed a low level of alignment with CEFR descriptors at the target level (CoE, 2020). It was not unexpected, however, the reason for the low level of alignment in overall speaking at the B1 level could be attributed to the design of the speaking tests, which aimed to test either production-based or interaction-based skills. Thus, the alignment rate of speaking skill, by combining both sub-skills, was lowered because objectives designed for production-based speaking tests did not correspond to the interaction-based descriptors of the CEFR. Moreover, for the speaking skill based on production, the tests aimed to target overall oral production, including sustained monologues: describing an experience and presenting a case (e.g., in a debate). However, other sub-scales within CEFR spoken production, such as sustained monologue: giving information, public announcement, and addressing audiences, were not assessed in the speaking tests. Also, the interaction-based speaking skill was established through overall oral interaction, understanding an interlocutor, conversation, informal discussion (with friends), formal discussion (meetings), goal-oriented cooperation (cooking together, discussing a document, organising an event, etc.), obtaining goods and services, information exchange, interviewing and being interviewed, however, using telecommunication, which was a missing aspect, could also be added to increase the alignment rate (CoE, 2020). This partial alignment was supported by the results of Sridhanyarat et al. (2021), who also adopted a semi-speaking format in their CEFR-aligned proficiency test. While the test used in their study reliably assessed basic speaking skills, it indirectly tested interaction, which highlighted the difficulty in achieving complete correspondence with CEFR spoken-interaction descriptors.

The moderate rate of alignment of listening skills at the B1 level included the objectives to test overall oral comprehension, understanding conversations between other people, and understanding audio (or signed) media and recordings. On the other hand, understanding as a member of a live audience had little contribution to the alignment, even if it was reported to be a significant aspect in listening by Alderson et al. (2006). However, the objectives corresponding to the scales—understanding announcements and instructions, and audio-visual comprehension (watching TV, film, and video)—were not integrated into the B1-level listening tests (CoE, 2020) and thus were not assessed at this level.

Writing skill at the B1 level yielded two results: (1) moderate alignment rates in both production-based writing and interaction-based speaking, and (2) a low level of alignment in general writing, production, and interaction combined, which was not an expected result. The aspects that mostly enhanced the alignment in production-based writing were overall written production, as well as reports and essays. However, creative writing had an average level of contribution. The interaction-based writing was improved by the correspondence to overall written interaction, notes, messages, and forms, except for correspondence (CoE, 2020). These results were in agreement with Zheng et al. (2016) in the sense that high alignment with CEFR descriptors could be achieved with the task types and scale coverage. They also supported the notion that CEFR-based writing evaluations could not be standardized, as CEFR descriptors were not concrete enough and open to different interpretations, which may affect inter-rater reliability. The alignment rate with the B1 level in writing could be improved by integrating writing tasks corresponding to the missing scales mentioned above. Additionally, the CEFR could propose writing task samples at the target levels (Zheng et al., 2016).

A low alignment rate emerged in the B1-level reading skill. The alignment was based on correspondence to the scales: overall reading comprehension and reading for orientation, as well as reading for information and argument. However, reading as a leisure activity had a slight contribution to the alignment while reading correspondence, and reading instructions, which was a specific skill in reading (Alderson et al., 2006), were underrepresented at the target level; thus, the increase in the alignment rates could be achieved in these aspects (CoE, 2020). Mediation resulted in a low level of alignment with the B1 level, which was in line with Lankina and Pect (2020), but more improvement was needed. Mediating a text was the only aspect included in the B1-level tests. The enhancement of this aspect and the integration of overall mediation, including mediating concepts, mediating group work, and mediating communication, would result in a higher alignment rate in B1-level mediation (CoE, 2020). As in the study by Kantarcioğlu (2022), university students engage in mediation activities, such as note-taking during listening and summarizing articles, which can be considered mediation tasks and included in the applied test. The integration of the tasks related to the aforementioned scales could help B1-level tests achieve CEFR standards.

Regarding B2-level examinations, the alignment rate of language use sections and speaking skills based on production was high, which may still be enhanced. Besides, production-based writing demonstrated a satisfactory alignment rate with the B2 level. However, moderate levels of alignment arose from the reading, listening, and general writing skills. Lastly, mediation, written interaction, and speaking had the lowest rate of alignment with the B2 level, requiring adaptations to meet CEFR standards (CoE, 2020). The findings related to mediation are consistent with the results of Lenz (2022), who found little contribution of mediation to the tasks. Both aspects that enhanced the correspondences to the B2 level and those that were not represented in the alignment would be discussed. The fact that Language

Use was highly aligned with the B2 level depended on the vocabulary range and grammatical accuracy; however, general linguistic range and vocabulary control were the aspects that still needed to be worked on. These results were partly in line with the findings of Baldwin and Apelgren (2018), who observed the focus on grammatical accuracy and vocabulary control in teacher assessments, despite the communicative focus of the CEFR descriptors. Moreover, orthographic control and phonological control were not represented in the language use tasks, but the CEFR linguistic competence required enhancement in the underrepresented aspects (CoE, 2020).

The writing skill demonstrated different results based on the type of assessment. A satisfactory alignment rate was observed in production-based writing, whereas interaction-based writing showed a low alignment rate at the B2 level. Thus, the alignment rate of writing skill in general was moderate, as expected. Based on written production scales, overall written production, and reports and essays, the highest contribution to the alignment was found in these areas. At the same time, creative writing established a moderate level of alignment. Additionally, in terms of written interaction scales, overall written interaction made a low contribution to the alignment, which also supported the alignment rate, as it was the only corresponding scale (CoE, 2020). However, the objectives that align with the scales — correspondence, notes, messages, and forms — could be taken into consideration for a higher level of alignment. As mentioned before, complete alignment with CEFR writing standards at the target level was challenging because the CEFR promotes communicative effectiveness in diverse contexts of writing in real life (Zheng et al., 2016).

The speaking skill also indicated various results based on the assessment type. A high alignment rate was observed in production-based speaking tests. In general, speaking skills resulted in a low level of alignment due to the absence of interaction-based speaking tests. Likewise, the semi-speaking section in the CEFR-based proficiency test created by Sridhanyarat et al. (2021) did not include any components of interaction, which limited its alignment with the B2 level. The alignment of production-based speaking skills was established through the full contribution of overall oral production, including sustained monologues that describe experiences and present a case (e.g., in a debate). The aspect of sustained monologue: giving information was also represented at the B2 level with a moderate level of contribution. However, public announcement and addressing the audience were not included in the task objectives at the B2 level tests, besides any spoken interaction scales (CoE, 2020). The reason why spoken interaction descriptors were not represented depended on the mode of assessment. However, the integration of interaction-based speaking tests could lead to a higher alignment with the B2 level.

As a receptive skill, reading skill demonstrated a low level of alignment with the B2 level, which was in line with the results of Sridhanyarat et al. (2021), emphasizing the focus on general comprehension rather than the higher-order reading tasks at the B2 level, despite the valid and reliable reading section of their test. The scales of reading for orientation and reading for information and argument showed correspondences in the tests. However, incorporating overall reading comprehension, reading correspondence, reading instructions, and reading as a leisure activity could enhance the reading tasks to achieve a B2 level (CoE, 2020).

Listening skill was the other receptive skill that demonstrated a low level of alignment with the B2 level. The alignment was founded on objectives corresponding to the scales: overall oral comprehension and understanding of audio (or signed) media and recordings, which had a significant impact on the alignment. The other scales, which enhanced the alignment,

were understanding as a member of a live audience, audio-visual comprehension-watching TV, film, and video, and understanding conversation between other people; the integration of these aspects at higher levels could enhance the alignment as they were the expected real-life listening skills (Alderson et al., 2006). Moreover, understanding announcements and instructions was not represented in the B2-level listening tests (CoE, 2020). However, a higher level of alignment could be achieved by incorporating listening tasks that cater to the aforementioned aspects.

Lastly, B2-level tests had a low level of mediation, which could be based on the complex structure of mediation skills in the assessment (CoE, 2020; Kartarcioğlu, 2022); however, the results were not supported by Lankina and Pect (2020) who observed that B2-level learners had a complex nature of mediation and applied a variety of descriptors of mediation regarding the CEFR. The results suggest that the task designs and contexts of the language tests may have a significant impact on the mediation, as the utilized tests in this study were inadequate, even for B2-level learners who were capable of handling them. The alignment was established through various scales: mediating a text, mediating concepts, and overall mediation. However, mediating group work and mediating communication could also be included at B2-level tests, as the written and spoken interaction were required and essential skills for B2 level (CoE, 2020). A higher alignment rate in mediation could be achieved by integrating missing aspects and incorporating more objectives into the corresponding scales.

5.1. Implications

The results of this study highlight the requirement for the proper use of the CEFR in order to design the language tests to assess actual proficiency. In the context of the current study, in which the CEFR-based textbooks were utilized and the aim was to achieve B2-level proficiency in English, the balance between the objectives of the tests at the intermediate level of English and the CEFR objectives should be achieved through integration of the objectives corresponding to various scales in the CEFR.

The current study provides significant insights for EFL lecturers in the testing offices of the SFL at universities, ELT departments at universities, and CoHE in Turkey. A crucial recommendation for EFL lecturers working in the testing offices of the SFL at universities is to consider whether the descriptors of the CEFR illustrative scales at the target level overlap with the objectives of the examinations. For this purpose, lecturers at the testing offices must be familiar with the CEFR descriptors at the target level. Therefore, in-service training and workshops are necessary to integrate the CEFR into language assessment. Taking action for the standardization of assessment was also recommended by Staub and Kırkgöz (2020), with a suggestion for day-to-day activities in institutions. ELT departments at universities should also take action by integrating a course related to the CEFR and its usage in language assessment into their curriculum. Reducing inconsistencies in the perception of proficiency levels regarding the CEFR and establishing more standardized guidelines for language assessment at all universities is recommended for CoHE in Turkey, as they are autonomous in preparing their language tests. The implications of the present study are of utmost importance to enhance the reliability and validity of language assessments and to achieve greater alignment with the CEFR.

5.2. Limitations

There are some limitations in the current study. All the language tests administered in the 2023-2024 academic year were included in the current study to represent the B1 and B2 levels, resulting in a lengthy data collection process. Moreover, the tests were not prepared

based on pre-determined objectives, which caused the data collection procedure to be prolonged as the researcher prepared the objective list for each test. Consequently, the results may not be generalized to all the language tests at the B1 and B2 levels of English, as they were internal tests at a university. Despite the limitations mentioned above, the current study is significant in the literature on aligning B1 and B2 level English tests with the learning outcomes of the CEFR.

5.3. Suggestions

Further research may adopt a mixed-method research design that could enable a more comprehensive understanding of language assessment processes with the help of more generalizable quantitative data. Expanding the scope of research by integrating curriculum design into assessment practices could contribute to a more holistic approach in language teaching and assessment procedures.

Acknowledgement

This study is derived from the doctoral dissertation of the first author, conducted under the supervision of the second author. The dissertation has not yet been formally defended.

Ethical Issues

The authors confirm that ethical approval was obtained from Hacettepe University (Decision Number: E-51944218-050-00003573465, Approval Date: May 31, 2024).

Conflict of Interest

The authors declared no conflict of interest.

References

- Alderson, J. C., Figueras, N., Kuijper, H., Nold, G., Takala, S., & Tardieu, C. (2006). Analysing tests of reading and listening in relation to the common European framework of reference: The experience of the Dutch CEFR construct project. *Language Assessment Quarterly: An International Journal*, 3(1), 3–30. https://doi.org/10.1207/s15434311laq0301_2
- Alderson, J. C. (2007). The CEFR and the need for more research. *The Modern Language Journal (MLJ)*, 91(4), 659–663. https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1540-4781.2007.00627_4.x
- Arikan, A. (2016). An examination of the EPOSTL's potential practical use in Turkey. *Artuklu Human and Social Science Journal*, 1(1), 76–80.
- Baldwin, R., & Apelgren, B. M. (2018). Can do and cannot do—CEFR inspired examination and assessment in a Swedish higher education context. *Apples: Journal of Applied Language Studies*, 12(2), 19–35. <https://doi.org/10.17011/apples/urn.201809144127>
- Baxter, P., & Jack, S. (2008). Qualitative case study methodology: Study design and implementation for novice researchers. *The Qualitative Report*, 13(4), 544–559. <https://doi.org/10.46743/2160-3715/2008.1573>
- British Council. (2015). *Türkiye'de yükseköğretim kurumlarındaki İngilizce eğitimi*. Ankara: British Council.
- Brown, H. D., & Abeywickrama, P. (2019). *Language assessment: Principles and classroom practices*. White Plains, NY: Pearson.
- Byram, M., & Parmenter, L. (2012). *The Common European Framework of Reference: The globalization of language education policy*. Bristol: Multilingual Matters.

- Council of Europe (CoE). (2001). *Common European Framework of Reference for Languages: Learning, teaching, assessment*. Strasbourg: CoE.
- Council of Europe (CoE). (2009). *Relating language examinations to the Common European framework of reference for languages: Learning, teaching, assessment (CEFR). A manual*. Strasbourg: CoE.
- Council of Europe (CoE). (2018). *The Common European Framework of Reference for Languages: Learning, Teaching, Assessment—Companion volume with new descriptors*. Strasbourg: CoE.
- Council of Europe (CoE). (2020). *Common European framework of reference for languages: Learning, teaching, assessment – Companion volume*. Strasbourg: CoE.
- Council of Higher Education. (n.d.). *History of the council of higher education*. CoHE. <https://eski.yok.gov.tr/en/institutional/history>
- Creswell, J. W., & Creswell, J. D. (2018). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches*. Thousand Oaks: Sage.
- Curle, S., Yuksel, D., Aizawa, I., Thompson, G., & Rakhshandehroo, M. (2024). Academic success in English Medium Instruction programmes in Turkey: Exploring the effect of gender, motivation, and English language proficiency. *International Journal of Educational Research*, 123. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijer.2023.102288>
- Davidson, F., & Fulcher, G. (2007). The common European framework of reference (CEFR) and the design of language tests: A matter of effect. *Language teaching*, 40(3), 231–241. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0261444807004351>
- Demirdöven, G. H. (2025). CEFR updates (2020)-based next-gen immersive learning in 5 steps. *Frontiers in Education*, 10, 1567249. <https://doi.org/10.3389/feduc.2025.1567249>
- Demirel, Ö. (2020). *CEFR-based language testing*. Ankara: Pegem.
- Dunifa, L. (2023). Evaluating oral English program for non-English major students: Focusing on self-assessment of students' speaking abilities and their needs. *Novitas-ROYAL (Research on Youth and Language)*, 17(2), 34–49. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10015757>
- Green, A. (2017). Linking tests of English for academic purposes to the CEFR: The score user's perspective. *Language Assessment Quarterly*, 15(1), 59–74. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15434303.2017.1350685>
- Hulstijn, J. H. (2007). The shaky ground beneath the CEFR: Quantitative and qualitative dimensions of language proficiency. *The Modern Language Journal (MLJ)*, 91(4), 663–667. https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1540-4781.2007.00627_5.x
- Jones, N., & Saville, N. (2009). European language policy: Assessment, learning, and the CEFR. *Annual Review of Applied Linguistics*, 29, 51–63. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0267190509090059>
- Kantarcıoğlu, E. (2022). The CEFR companion volume and mediation: An Assessment perspective. In D. Little & N. Figueras (Eds.), *Reflecting on the common European framework of reference for languages and its companion volume* (pp. 171–184). Bristol: Multilingual Matters. <https://doi.org/10.21832/9781800410206-019>
- Khalifa, H., & French, A. (2009). Aligning Cambridge ESOL examinations to the CEFR: Issues & practice. *Cambridge ESOL Research Notes*, 37, 10–14.
- Lankina, O. Y., & Pect, Y. V. (2020). Classroom-based assessment of group discussion: Challenges and opportunities. *CEFR Journal Research and Practice*, 3, 116–125. <https://doi.org/10.37546/JALTSIG.CEFR3-8>
- Lenz, P. (2022). Some thoughts about the testing of mediation. In D. Little & N. Figueras (Eds.), *Reflecting on the common European framework of reference for languages and its companion volume* (pp. 113–120). Bristol: Multilingual Matters.

- Mirici, İ. H., & Şengül, F. (2020). Assessment in EFL classes based on the CEFR principles. *Bartın University Journal of Faculty of Education*, 9(2), 252–263. <https://doi.org/10.14686/buefad.655985>
- North, B. (2014). Putting the common European framework of reference to good use. *Language Teaching*, 47(2), 228–249. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0261444811000206>
- North, B., & Piccardo, E. (2023). Aligning language frameworks: An example with the CLB and CEFR. *Language Assessment Quarterly*, 20(2), 143–165. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15434303.2023.2184266>
- Özdemir-Yılmaz, M. (2022). Direct access to English-medium higher education in Turkey: Variations in entry language scores. *Dil Eğitimi ve Araştırmaları Dergisi*, 8(2), 325–345. <https://doi.org/10.31464/jlere.1105651>
- Pekdoğan, T., Udriştiou, M. T., Puiu, S., Yıldızhan, H., & Hruška, M. (2023). A multi-country statistical analysis covering Turkey, Slovakia, and Romania in an educational framework. *Sustainability*, 15(24), 16735. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su152416735>
- Presidency of the Republic of Turkey. (2016). *Regulation on the principles to be observed in foreign language teaching in higher education institutions*. Retrieved May 12, 2024, from <https://www.mevzuat.gov.tr/mevzuat?MevzuatNo=21475&MevzuatTur=7&MevzuatTertip=5>
- Sakarya-Akbulut, H., & Mirici, İ. H. (2024). An investigation on EFL students' perceptions of task-based language assessment in the blended learning environment. *Novitas-ROYAL (Research on Youth and Language)*, 18(2), 12–28. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13225030>
- Saral, N. Ç., & Balçıklan, C. (2025). Digesting centralized curricula in Türkiye: How literate are English language teachers? *Novitas-ROYAL (Research on Youth and Language)*, 19(1), 81–99. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15210570>
- Schoch, K. (2020). Case study research. In G. J. Burkholder, K. A. Cox, L. M. Crawford, & C. L. Hitchcock (Eds.), *Research design and methods: An applied guide for the scholar-practitioner* (pp. 245–258). Thousand Oaks: Sage.
- Sridhanyarat, K., Pathong, S., Suranakkharin, T., & Ammaralikit, A. (2021). The Development of STEP, the CEFR-Based English Proficiency Test. *English Language Teaching*, 14(7), 95–106. <https://doi.org/10.5539/elt.v14n7p95>
- Staub, D., & Kirkgöz, Y. (2019). Standards assessment in English language teacher education. *Novitas-ROYAL (Research on Youth and Language)*, 13(1), 47–61.
- Yüce, E., & Mirici, İ. H. (2022). Self-assessment in EFL classes of secondary education in Türkiye: The common European framework of reference for languages (CEFR)-based implementations. *Pegem Journal of Education and Instruction*, 13(1), 349–359. <https://doi.org/10.47750/pegegog.13.01.38>
- Zheng, Y., Zhang, Y., & Yan, Y. (2016). *Investigating the practice of the common European framework of reference for languages (CEFR) outside Europe: A case study on the assessment of writing in English in China*. London: British Council.
- Zorba, M. G., & Arikan, A. (2016). A study of Anatolian High Schools' 9th grade English language curriculum in relation to the CEFR. *Uşak Üniversitesi Eğitim Araştırmaları Dergisi*, 2(2) 13–24. <https://doi.org/10.29065/usakead.232436>
- Zorba, M. G. (2025). (Re)locating Türkiye's intercultural stance through juxtaposing non-Western and Western perspectives. In H. R'boul (Ed.), *Intercultural communication education and research in the Middle East and North Africa* (pp.66–84). London: Routledge.